

STUDY OF DIRECT OUT-OF-PLANE TENSILE TEST METHOD FOR CFRP LAMINATES WITH DIFFERENT THICKNESS

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SUMMARY

Finite element analyses and experiments of unidirectional CFRP laminates were carried out in order to investigate the effect of specimen configuration on the out-of-plane tensile strength. The present study focuses on the flatwise tension test using spool column specimens for the measurement of out-of-plane tensile strength.

Keywords: test method, out-of-plane properties, interlaminar properties, tensile strength, CFRP

INTRODUCTION

CFRPs are attractive structural materials in various applications because of their high performance characteristics. For wide applications, various properties of CFRPs are required to evaluate. For easy evaluation, various measuring procedures are standardized. However, direct out-of-plane tensile test method for CFRP laminates remained as a theme required to be established. Last year, ASTM standardized the out-of-plane tensile test.[1]

In order to effectively use the ASTM standard, we believe that many basic data are required. Several studies were reported on how to determine the out-of-plane tensile properties.[2] An overview of out-of-plane test methods was given by M J Lodeiro et al.[2] However, because of difficulties in performing out-of-plane tensile tests for thin specimen, the standardized method have actually used in a few applications. This study focuses on “How to perform the out-of-plane tensile tests using thin cylindrical column specimen.

EXPERIMENTS and ANALYSIS

Experiments (Specimen configuration, Test procedure, Test results)

The specimen was composed of CFRP IM600/#133 (unidirectional Carbon / Epoxy prepreg) with a stacking sequence of $[0^\circ]_n$. Six types of spool-shaped specimens were prepared (see Fig.1) by changing the minimum diameter and thickness. The minimum diameter of specimens was varied to 6.25 mm, 12.5 mm, and 18.75 mm, and the thickness of specimens 8 mm and 16 mm. Adhesive film, AF163, was used for bonding the specimen to test fixture made of steel blocks. Fig. 2 illustrates the setup of the test fixture and the specimen. The tensile tests of the spool specimen were carried out based on ASTM D 7291. Actual test procedure adopted was as follows,

1. Bonding specimen to two end-tab-blocks, during which axial alignment was adjusted using a special jig.
2. Assembling specimen-bonded end-tab-blocks, adjustment fixture and end-plate with pivoting joint.
3. Fixing the assembled specimen and fixtures to grips of test machine (INSTRON 8500)
4. Loading specimen at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min.

The nominal out-of-plane tensile strengths were calculated from the fracture force divided by the minimum cross-sectional area at center of specimen. Fig. 3 shows the relationship between nominal strength of spool specimens and a center diameter. The nominal strength increases with decrease in the center diameter and with increase in the thickness.

Fig. 1 Configurations of test specimens.

Fig. 2 Illustration & picture of test setup.

Fig. 3 The Nominal Strength as a function of the minimum diameter.

ANALYSIS (Analysis models, Loading conditions, Analysis results)

The stress distributions generated in specimens under load was estimated using a finite element method. The finite element commercial code, ABAQUS 6, was used for the calculations. The finite element models covered the half region of a specimen and adhesive layer considering the symmetry of the specimen shape loading condition, where the midplane (see Fig. 1) of the specimen was constrained in the z-direction. All the geometries were modelled. 4-nodes tetrahedral elements with reduced integration were used for the analysis models of the spool specimens. The relation between the nominal stress and the maximum out-of-plane stress was estimated from the result of the analysis. The loading conditions consisted of tensile displacement applied in the out-of-plane direction to the top surface of the adhesive lamina.

Fig.4 shows the typical results of finite element analysis. From this figure, out-of-plane maximum stress appears on the periphery of the minimum cross-section. Then, the stress ratio is defined as the nominal stress divided by the maximum stress. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the stress ratio and specimen center diameter.

Fig. 4 Out-of-plane stress contour of the spool specimen.

Fig. 5 The stress ratio as a function of a diameter of minimum cross-section.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As decreasing center diameter and increasing thickness, nominal strength increases. This tendency for nominal strength was consistent with analysis results. Within the cases of the same thickness, when the minimum diameter decreased, the stress ratio approached 1. These are thought to be caused by the following reasons; the change in the stress decreases (in midplane), the aspect ratio (diameter/thickness) of the specimen becomes small and the state of the stress approaches the same state as that of uniaxial stress. It is expected that accuracy out-of-plane strength is higher than the experimental results in this study.

References

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